

A Sanshin Musical Performance Assistive Device for People with Physical Disabilities of the Extremities

Satone Yamashiro, Hideyuki Uehara and Hiroki Higa

Abstract: This paper describes a sanshin musical performance assistive device for people with physical disabilities of the extremities. Sanshin is an Okinawan three-stringed musical instrument. We had developed portable assistive devices to press strings against board of sanshin and its controllers. In the experiments, some participants played the sanshin using the assistive devices. It was found from the experimental results that two persons with muscular dystrophies could appropriately performed music using the sanshins with the previous assistive devices, and that two able-bodied persons could smoothly and steadily play the sanshins using the improved assistive device with the photoelectric sensor-based controller.

Keywords: Sanshin; Musical instrument; Assistive device; Physical disabilities

I. INTRODUCTION

Anyone can enjoy playing the musical instruments. Playing the musical instruments, we feel a sense of achievement, joyfulness, and appreciate the fun of playing. People who are suffering from progressive disorders, such as muscular dystrophy (MD) and amyotrophic lateral sclerosis (ALS), however, give up playing the musical instruments because of their physical disabilities of the extremities. To play the musical instruments leads to a condition known as improvement of quality of their lives (QOLs). Using the hands and fingers is good for rehabilitation. Since the time of Aristotle and Plato, it has been known that music has a healing influence which can affect health and behavior [1].

People with severe disabilities have some interface options, for example, tongue-controlled interfaces [2], [3] and interface using the movements of the mouth muscles [4]. It is difficult to sing songs when installing sensors in and around the mouth. We have developed a sanshin musical performance assistive devices for people with physical disabilities of the extremities. In addition, push-button-based controllers and photoelectric sensor-based controller have been created. In this paper, we introduce the sanshin musical performance assistive device with some controllers.

II. METHOD

A. Sanshin

A sanshin is an Okinawan traditional and popular three-stringed musical instrument. A sanxian, Chinese musical instrument, was brought from China at the end of the 14th century, and it became the original model of sanshin in the Kingdom of Ryukyu [5], [6] (present Okinawa). Sanshin is generally composed of a neck, three strings and body covered by the leather of a python.

A. System configuration

A system configuration of a sanshin musical performance assistive device is illustrated in Fig. 1. The device consists of an actuator unit to press strings of sanshin, its controller and DC power supply adapter. We made the assumption that a sanshin is placed with the three-string side facing up on a table, and that user can pluck strings by her/his own hand freely and voluntarily.

Fig. 2 shows the actuator unit which is mainly made from aluminum plates. It is equipped with four servos (blue rectangular-shaped objects) and a microcontroller which generates PWM waveforms to control each of them. A lever arm is mounted on a rotating shaft of each servo to efficiently press the strings of sanshin. Unlatching and opening its upper frame, the device can be readily attached to the neck part of commercially available sanshin. Musical performance using sanshin with our assistive device can be performed in any place as long as the stage has a table and DC power supply of 6 V.

Fig. 1 System configuration (top view) of sanshin musical performance assistive device for people with physical disabilities of the extremities [7]. Actuator unit is a tool to press down on sanshin's strings to assist user's musical performance.

(a) Front view

(b) Side view

Fig. 2 Actuator unit.

III. EXPERIMENT

Two persons with muscular dystrophies (MDs) participated in the experiment. They were hospitalized in Okinawa National Hospital, belonged to musical club there, and had experiences to play the sanshin. It was one of their recreational activities for them to play the sanshin. They could pluck strings of their own sanshins with their right hands, however hardly press the strings with their left hands due to their limitations in ranges of motion. When they get around in their powered wheelchairs, they manipulate them with their left thumbs. Focusing on the fact and ranges of motions in their left thumbs, two controllers were designed and made, as shown in Fig. 3. Each controller has four push-button switches which activate four servos in the actuator unit. Outer shapes of their controllers were customized so that the individuals with MDs could push all of switches comfortably. We asked them to play the sanshin using our devices. The study was approved by the Institutional Review Board of the Okinawa National Hospital. Two subjects gave their informed consent.

(a) For subject A.

(b) For subject B.

Fig. 3 Controllers [7] for sanshin musical performance assistive device. Black round portions are push-button switches to activate servos in the actuator unit.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

In our preliminary experiments, we confirmed that the persons with MDs could press strings of the sanshins by pushing each switch on the controllers. There was a slight time lag between pushing a switch on the controller and pressing the strings by one of lever arms in the actuator unit. We provided them with the assistive devices, and they continued to play the sanshin using our assistive devices. After a great deal of

practice to play the sanshin using the devices, they started to perform live activities. Fig. 4 shows the musical performance on the stage at the music town Oto-ichiba concert hall where a music festival was held. They gave actively and energetically their musical performance using the assistive devices to a large number of audiences.

(a) Performing the sanshin with the assistive device.

(b) Except for the person in the middle, two persons sitting at either end of the stage were playing the sanshins using the assistive devices. One of the devices is showing on a large screen on the stage.

Fig. 4 A live musical performance using the assistive devices at musical festival in a concert hall [7].

V. IMPROVEMENTS OF THE MUSICAL PERFORMANCE ASSISTIVE DEVICE

We redesigned the musical performance assistive device to respond to users' requests. The following three features were added to the assistive device.

First, an angle adjustment function was embedded in the actuator unit, as shown in Fig. 5 (a). Each user has limitation in the range of motion in her/his wrist joint due to her/his disability, and has a preferable position and angle of the right hand when she/he plucks

strings of sanshin. The wrist angles depend on the individual. This angle adjustment function allows users to make minute adjustments to the face angle of the three-string side of sanshin. Its face angle continuously varies within the ranges from 0 deg to 32 deg.

(a) Angle adjustment function of the actuator unit.

(b) Fine adjustment function of servo position

Fig. 5 Incorporated functions of the actuator unit of the assistive device.

Secondly, the actuator unit incorporated a fine adjustment function of servo position, as shown in Fig. 5 (b). Sanshin is a fretless stringed musical instrument, and is set a bridge when playing. The bridge is called "Uma" in sanshin, and is a part that supports sanshin's strings and transmits the vibration of those strings to its body part, such as a violin or cello. Positions where to hold down the strings are slightly changed when the bridge is put slightly different position. The fine adjustment function enables users to finely adjust position to press the strings. Furthermore, depending on some pieces of music which is played by the sanshin, the position of the third lever arm is needed to be changed to a small extent. Using our assistive device is capable of dealing with this change immediately.

Thirdly, photoelectric sensor-based controller was also built. One of persons with MDs gradually reduced

his thumb's range of motion due to the progressive disease. It became extremely difficult for him to manipulate the push-button-based controller. This is the reason why we made the new controller for the musical assistive device. Fig. 6 (a) shows its appearance. It looks like the push-button-based controller as shown in Fig. 3 (a). Fig. 6 (b) indicates a schematic diagram of the photoelectric sensor-based controller. A photo reflector, TPR-105F [8], is a photoelectric sensor which has a pair of infrared LED and photoelectric receiver. In the photoelectric sensor-based controller, four photo reflector sensors were used instead of the mechanical switches. When covering a sensor window with the fingertip, the photoelectric receiver detects reflection of the infrared light. It then generates output signal, which allows a servo to be activated by the microcontroller Arduino UNO. An optical filter, Fuji filter IR-90 (Fujifilm Corporation), has functions of absorbing visual light and of transmitting infrared light, and is attached on the four sensor windows to prevent the optical controller's malfunction caused by light which comes in from the outside.

(a) Its appearance.

(b) Its principle.

Fig. 6 Photoelectric sensor-based controller.

Fig. 7 Experimental result when one of able-bodied subjects is playing the sanshin with photoelectric sensor-based controller.

Two able-bodied persons took part in the experiment as volunteers. They were asked to play the sanshin using the assistive device with photoelectric sensor-based controller. An example experimental result is shown in Fig. 7. One of the subjects also played the sanshin at a poster session in the international conference site [7], [9]. Some of attendees at the conference manipulated the device using the photoelectric sensor-based controller. It was clear that everyone could control our assistive device even using optically based interfaces without applying a great force. It is suggested that the musical performance assistive device described in this paper will be useful for persons with disabilities of the extremities as a way to play the sanshin. The EMG-based and EEG-based controllers [10]-[12] will be better options, when it comes to those for severely compromised patients. These are our works in progress. Some of experimental results will be reported in another paper.

IV. CONCLUSION

We presented the sanshin musical performance assistive devices with some controllers. It was confirmed from the experimental results that the persons with MDs could play the sanshins using our assistive devices with mechanical based controller successfully, and that the able-bodied subjects could perform music using the improved assistive device with the optical-based controller with no difficulty. Further experiment of optically based controller with persons

with MDs would be needed for our future works.

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